

**THE SOVEREIGN METAMORPHOSIS: SUMITRA AS A
PARAMOUNT EXAMPLE OF FEMALE AUTHORITY IN TAGORE'S
*THE KING AND THE QUEEN***

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ABSTRACT

*The present paper discusses Rabindranath Tagore's drama *The King and the Queen*, with a special emphasis on Queen Sumitra as a model of female authority. As Tagore's first tragedy, published in 1889, the play dives into the characters' personal and political dynamics and presents a sophisticated story that weaves together themes of love, duty, power, and tradition. The female characters of the play seem to be fighting against the ancient societal restrictions that were created to bind women to the diplomatic perceptions of society under the guise of so-called customs and rituals. Undoubtedly, Tagore's literature, particularly drama, reflects his vision, drawing a comprehensive picture of Indian womanhood that, while not perfect, is surely desirable and close to the heart. However, this study examines Sumitra's character in depth to see how Tagore uses her to question established gender stereotypes and demonstrate the transforming power of female leadership.*

Keywords: Rabindranath Tagore, Sumitra, Women Empowerment, Indian Womanhood, Sacrifice, Historical Tragedy, Stereotypes, Political Dynamics, Modern Feminist Ideals, Tragic Heroine.

Introduction

Woman's home may have been shattered, but woman is not, and cannot, herself be killed. It is not that woman is merely seeking her freedom of livelihood, struggling against man's monopoly of business, but man's monopoly of civilization where he is breaking her heart every day and desolating her life. She must restore the lost social balance by putting the full weight of woman in to the creation of human world. ...The time has come when woman's responsibility has become greater than before, when her field of work has far transcended the domestic sphere of life. (Personality: Woman vol. II, 415)

Rabindranath Tagore's play *The King and the Queen* is a complex drama written and published in the year 1889. This is Tagore's first tragedy, and it is notable for successfully depicting his most dominant female character, Queen Sumitra. The play is the first dramatic expression of Tagore's political ideas. It gained high global praise for its original dramatic content and spontaneous depiction of the nineteenth-century Bengali Renaissance. The play's

topic is governed by variably depicted conflicts and illusions. “The conflict in this play is between love and duty, between a vain and infatuated man, and a proud and humane woman.” (K. Kriplani, 127)

Socio-Political Significance of the Play and Sovereign Ascendancy

The play *The King and the Queen* is remarkable for showing the extraordinary female characters in the play, and shares credit for determining women's powerful role in society. In this play, Tagore has succeeded in painting a full picture of femininity through the three faces. The dramatist created the brave, audacious, and graceful queen Sumitra. The play has grown in popularity due to its diverse representations of other female characters, particularly the beautiful, loyal, and compassionate Ila and the self-centered, offensive, and wicked Revati. The play portrays a conflict between love and responsibility. The emphasis has been placed on King Vikram's unbridled approach to satisfying his ardent needs, as well as the immensely sincere exposure of duties by Queen Sumitra. Sumitra's captivating physical charm has such a powerful hold on Vikram's heart and mind that he is forced to completely abandon his duties as a King. This insane obsession with his wife, which plays a damaging role, not only threatens his peace of mind but also causes chaos and clamour in his kingdom. The King is limited to his own life and tends to encircle Sumitra's existence as a wife and cherished, confounding his love with desire. On the contrary, his loving wife Sumitra is fully aware of her job as her subject's mother. She attempts unsuccessfully to make her negligent husband realise his royal duties. However, Sumitra grows restless to know the dreadful situation of her state. Devadutta, one of the King's loyal officials, warns her of the poor subject's pitiful plight, exposing a bare picture of the outside world, in which starving inhabitants beg for bread and the country is administered by foreigners who intend to rebel against the King. Sumitra refuses to accept this embarrassing truth about her kingdom and vows to battle against all of the misfortunes ignored by her husband time and time again. She decides to take the help of his brother Kumarsen, the King of Kashmir.

Tagore delves into Sumitra's admirable bravery in this work. Unfortunately, she and her brother are forced to confront the disastrous consequences of their honest and determined efforts. In the end “The monumental egotism of the King is shattered and the bold Queen dominates the play.” (Neeru Tandon, 137) The numerous clashes in personal and political life resulted in the most tragic conclusion for the two extraordinarily devoted lovers, followed by the King's repentance. The play *The King and the Queen*, which Tagore claims is the first technically crafted piece of drama, does an excellent job of capturing the spirit of the Renaissance. Krishna Kriplani comments on the theme and presentation of the dramatic work, comparing it to Shakespeare's technique: “[...] his drama Raja O Rani (in blank verse) may be considered his nearest approach to a Shakespearian model, that is, plenty of action, much of it violent, contrast of characters and an inevitable sub-plot enlivened by intrigue.” (Kriplani, 143)

The play is a remarkable account of a woman's unwavering bravery and sacrifice. The play has undoubtedly been built around the queen Sumitra, the strongest woman. She begins the play with the glorious brightness of the morning sun, urging the entire world to accept the new face of woman with her delicate womanly grace and fully awakened sensibility. And she ends it like the silent and deep nightfall of human life, with her timeless feminine goodness. Sumitra's demeanour exudes unwavering bravery, and she sacrifices both her marriage and her happiness for the sake of others. She identifies with Tagore's image of a modern,

energetic woman. For the benefit of society and to defend a woman's multifarious position, she refuses to minimise her role within the limits of a wife and beloved. She is ready to take on the obligations of a royal mother, letting go of the limits imposed by her husband. Sumitra is a woman who understands how to make her existence and position dignified in a male-dominated culture through brave and daring actions. Tagore's goal in writing this play is to educate readers on the differences between true love and passion, personal affairs and societal calls, rights, and duties. By inventing the brilliantly positioned conflicting characters as King Vikram and Queen Sumitra, Tagore has accomplished establishing the ever-dominant reality of the world that the splendour of pure love can only be increased when it comes together with the correct association of the feelings of self-sacrifice, dedicatedly performed duties and responsibilities. Tagore, remarking on the poor chemistry of the husband-wife relationship, and specifically on Vikram's approach towards his love impulses, emphasises: "They seek love for pleasure, and miss love in the process; only happiness disappears; such is the mystery of illusion." (Tagore, *Kabir Bhanita*, 46)

Tagore's Sumitra defines the definition of a true kingly attitude and love. The escape from duty deceives both God and oneself. Sumitra believes that the feeling that overwhelms all of a man's senses and acts as a deviating force against duties and responsibilities is not a legitimate interpretation of love and genuine emotions. Sumitra makes her husband realise the importance of one's moral standings by forcibly admitting that for an individual, the well-being of others comes before one's selfish ambitions, and this is especially crucial for a person who is gifted with the obligations of a King.

Understanding Thematic Tapestry of Tagore's Narrative from a Feminine Perspective

The opening scene of the play reveals the core premise of the play, in which the King is no longer a King, but rather a passionate lover who is unconcerned about the issues of the state and its citizens but is irritated by his loving wife's delayed response to his romantic urges questioning: "Why have you delayed in coming to me for so long, my love?" Sumitra's response provides a comprehensive understanding of the idea that Tagore wishes to present to us: "Do you not know, my King, that I am utterly yours, wherever I am? It was your house, and its service, that kept me away from your presence, but not from you." The play's heroine has constructed a convincing picture of a woman's multifaceted position, one of a devoted wife as well as a whole human being. The talk between the two will form a complete picture when the king further expresses: "Leave the house, and its service, alone. My heart cannot spare you for my world, I am jealous of its claims." (*Rabindra Rachnavali: Sacrifice and Other Plays*, 133) The King wants the Queen to concentrate completely on her duty as a wife, ignoring the world and its issues. He lives a kingly life, full of luxuries, and has delegated state responsibilities to officials. He feels uneasy for the Queen, who is becoming increasingly anxious about the world. Sumitra attempts to fulfill every duty, whether as a wife or queen, but she fails to demonstrate her commitment. The King's passionate advances "Alas, my darling, where have vanished those days of unalloyed joy, when we first met in love; ... You had sweet shyness in your eyelids, like dew drop on the tip of a flower-petal, and the smile flickered on your lips like a timid evening lamp in the breeze," get a reply "But then we were scarcely more than a boy and a girl; and today we are the King and the Queen." (134)

Tagore has succeeded in establishing a highly crucial position in which a husband, disregards his wife's interest, and examines her emotions, which is undoubtedly a difficult environment for a woman to navigate "You are my King, my husband, and I am content to

follow your steps. Do not shame me by putting me before your kingship” (135) throughout the talk, we only see Sumitra as a dedicated queen, whereas Vikram is merely a passionate lover who is still living in the past. Vikram's love is depicted as ardent and free of kingly responsibilities, whereas Sumitra distinguishes between love and duty. Sumitra's remarkable responsiveness to the King's intense impulses heightens his anxiety. Sumitra's response shows a human's high moral perceptions, while Tagore, through Sumitra, attempts to establish the ultimate truth as he expressed in the popular poem *Sadhana*:

Want of love is a degree of callousness; for love is the perfection of consciousness. We do not love because we do not comprehend, or rather we do not comprehend because we do not love. For love is the ultimate meaning of everything around us.” (Das, Sadhana, 321)

The crisis escalates due to Vikram's refusal to address state issues, and the King's refusal to prioritise them. Sumitra, adamant about helping her people, seeks advice from Devadutta, a friend and well-wisher of the King, about chaos churning outside the palace. Devadutta argues that hungry people are creating the noise, causing inner frustration due to the King's indifference towards the pain of the people who are forced to die due to hunger and other basic needs. Tagore's Sumitra is a realistic representation of a woman's dual personality, marked by sympathy and compassion. Sumitra, once accused of having a ruthless heart, is now seen as a mother who is concerned about her people's well-being. She ignores personal tragedies and concentrates on the betterment of her people. A woman's heavenly grace is visible as she strives to meet the high expectations of her people. Sumitra is now regarded as a mother, guarding the goodness and welfare of society.

In this scene, Tagore vividly depicts the oppressed and impoverished class in India, underscoring the difficulties they face due to their ignorance of basic needs. Sumitra, who focuses on suffering, tries to figure out why their state is so terrible even if there is enough land. Frustrated with the situation, the Queen chooses to present the issue to the King, assuming he is unaware of it in a practical sense. The dramatist himself has focused on the point in his work *Sadhana* saying: “To live the life of goodness is to live the life of all. Pleasure is for one's own self, but goodness is concerned with the happiness of all humanity.” (*Sadhana: The Problem of Evil*, 302)

Sumitra, a caring queen, is determined to alleviate the pain of her subjects, claiming to be the mother of her people. However, Vikram, unaware of the kingdom's deteriorating state, is focused on fulfilling his romantic desires. Sumitra disregards the King's advice and neglects the King's suggestion. The Queen's carelessness fails to bring the poor people's concerns to the King's attention, leading to accusations of Devadutta's deviance. The economic conditions of the state have become more critical, but the King is unable to accurately assess the situation. Sumitra insists on Vikram's attention to the state's growing misery, despite the King's inability to judge the situation accurately. After several failed attempts, Sumitra takes over the charge and sends summons to foreign rulers, but they refuse her commands. This rejection exacerbates her wounded self-esteem, making her more determined to follow her plan. Vikram, knowing of his power and strength, admits that his love for Sumitra has rendered him unable to think beyond her presence. Sumitra, unable to persuade her husband of his duty, decides to leave Vikram and joins her brother Kumarsen, the King of Kashmir. Vikram accuses Devadutta of promoting the Queen, and she leaves the palace. The King is unprepared for such a brave move and hopes his wife will not disregard

her. He reveals his frustration saying: “Take you flight, woman, day and night, homeless, loveless, without rest and peace.” (153) Vikram attempts to silence the public by paying Sumitra enormous money. After several failed attempts, Sumitra assumes over and sends summons to foreign monarchs, but they refuse her commands. This rejection exacerbates her wounded self-esteem, making her more determined to follow out her plan. Vikram, knowing of his power and strength, admits that his love for Sumitra has rendered him unable to think beyond her presence. Sumitra, unable to persuade her husband of his duty, decides to leave Vikram and seek the assistance of her brother Kumarsen, the King of Kashmir. Vikram accuses Devadutta of promoting the Queen, and she leaves the palace. The King is unprepared for such a brave move and hopes his wife would not disregard her saying “My revenge? You shall know it.”(156) Tagore's writings reflect a man's longing for honour and glory, motivated by a need to appease his ego and shattered emotions. He delves inside the human mind, demonstrating that love may sacrifice life, whereas hatred can destroy even the most valuable emotion.

As the story progresses, we observe Kumarsen's uncle Chandrasen's intentions with his wife Revati to incite the King's wrath against Kumarsen. Chandrasen, greedy and conceited, desires the crown of Kashmir, and Revati is a hardhearted, selfish woman. The King assures Chandrasen that he only wants Kumarsen to give up power to teach Sumitra a lesson. The Chief Man of Trichur introduces Ila, a beautiful woman, into the King's life, turning his bitterness into sensitive feelings and reigniting his latent love. Tagore cleverly reversed the situation by introducing a woman who becomes the catalyst for the King's sensible feelings to be restored. Tagore draws a striking contrast between the two women: one becomes the cause of the war, while the other is portrayed as the Goddess of peace and tranquility. Sumitra identifies herself as the sole cause of the King's awakening and acknowledgment of manhood. While Ila becomes the catalyst for restoring the suppressed nobleness of a proud man. She innocently remarks, "I owe you my life and heavens happiness."(174) The King promises Ila that he will do everything to bring her beloved Kumarsen to her. Vikram sees Kumarsen at the height of love, where only fortunate persons are positioned. The King, who has won the war, has become his victim and struggles to achieve a woman's love. Kumarsen, who has been defeated in the war, has finally reached the untouchable heights of love. The King's aimless passion and emotions are taking shelter in the realization of true love. The King allows his soldiers to draw back his army to conclude the war but still feels something waiting for serious attention. He commands Devadutta to find Kumarsen and inform him about the peace. The King's love and emotions for the queen are balanced and true. In the last scene, the King arranges a royal wedding festival for Kumarsen and his wife Ila. Sumitra reveals that Kumarsen has sent his proud head as a sign of his victory over worldly humiliations. Sumitra informs the King about Kumarsen's bravery and how it was not acceptable to him to surrender her sister's pride. And finally, he conquered the battle of life by defeating material power. The play ends with the pathetic note: “Sire, no longer your Queen; for merciful death has claimed me.”(181)

Sumitra Embodying an Exegesis of Sovereign Ascendancy and Female Empowerment

Sumitra, Ila, and Revati are three female characters who play key parts in this play. Sumitra is the main character, exhibiting courage and persistence in charting the right road and even fighting against her kin. Sumitra, unlike Vikram, who is unaware of the gravity of the situation, is Tagore's strongest female character. She manages the entire affair despite her husband, a King's laziness, and is willing to shoulder all of his responsibilities. Tagore

expresses his profound sense of duty and sacrifice through Sumitra, highlighting the drama's female characters' courage and determination. Overall, the characters' depictions emphasise the play's complicated relationships and societal intricacies. Sumitra teaches Vikram the true meaning of love and the difference between desire and duty. She feels that family and the world expect something from everyone and that the King and Queen bear a greater level of duty. True love necessitates the sacrifice of own interests in favour of duty. Sumitra distinguishes between duty and personal affairs, prompting Vikram to devote his happiness to the welfare of his subject. On the other hand, Vikram refuses to give up his love impulses, whilst Sumitra is adamant about his kingly obligations “Love me truly by not making your love extravagant; for truth can be offered to be simple” whereas king demands “No more vain words, Queen the birds’ nests are silent with love. Let lips keep guard upon lips and allow not words to clamour.” (135) The male psyche, which has long held the right to establish or break relationships, has gripped him. He is not able to accept any other reactions ignited by the passionate love that can lead to a man dedicating everything for his beloved when it is met with a speechless acceptance. “In The King and the Queen the defiance of Sumitra is aimed at rescuing the nation from orthodox king’s negligence.” (Tandon, 138) Despite being a woman, Sumitra shows no concern for her kin, who are to blame for the state's misfortune. The queen's attitude promotes the highly revered notion that a King should ignore his sorrows and joys to determine his subjects' happiness. The King, overwhelmed by sensuous desires, disregards all else in this world. He feels no sympathy for others and instead criticises Sumitra for ignoring his feelings for the sake of worldly matters. The King orders her to keep away from governmental concerns. He shows his displeasure at Sumitra's suggestion to make everything right.

Tagore's play highlights the exceptional potential of women, who challenge male-dominated society through their courage, determination, and grace. Sumitra, a woman, is a prime example of such a woman, who uses her inner sublime power to protect her state with strength and wisdom. Despite being considered weaker, Sumitra breaks the age-old myth of being more loving than men, asserting her divine power in her life and actions. When her husband loses his manly nature, Sumitra realises her divine power and holds her womanly potential strong. The irony lies in the King's pursuit of sensual fulfillment and the Queen's high regard for duties and self-sacrifices. Sumitra resigns her tenderness for the responsibilities of a queen and plays the role of a confident woman. When she realizes her husband's true sense of duties is not being realised, she decides to leave her husband for the good of him. Sumitra admits her pain and feels great agony when talking to Vikram. The King admits that he cannot exercise his powers for his duties due to his love for Sumitra. She bitterly criticizes herself for this embarrassment, saying, "Hate me, King, forget me. I shall bear it bravely, but do not wreck your manhood against a woman's charms." (145) The queen's enterprising approach leads to high prizes, causing her to lose happiness and peace in her personal life. This conflict results in their separation and a disaster for the kingdom. Sumitra, always ready to dedicate herself to him, blames her mind for her husband's negligence, causing a disaster for the kingdom. According to K.R.S. Iyengar: “Tagore was seized by this idea and he wished to incarnate it in a drama presenting the evolution of human love from the physical to the spiritual.” (47) Because of his blind love for his wife, he lost her forever. “Vikram misses the truth while transgressing the bounds of reality in love.” (*Kabir Bhanita*, 45) Sumitra, a woman, faced the most difficult task of carrying the dead head of her brother Kumarsen before the King, a task she could not do when alive. Sumitra's love for her

brother's honor led her to face the most horrible truth of her life, especially for a woman. She knew that death was preferable to dishonour, as she accepted death for herself in place of an undignified life. As a sister, Sumitra couldn't bear the thought of her brother being insulted by her husband, as both relations held distinct importance for her. Kumarsen sacrificed his life for his honor and subject, and Sumitra carried Kumarsen's head to the King. After doing the daring job, Sumitra couldn't live for a single moment, as the pain was unbearable for her. Sumitra is Tagore's strongest presentation. She is continuously trying to make her partner comprehend the depth of her feelings for him. She freely recognises her duties as a wife while also remembering her duty as a 'Queen Mother', who is burdened with some unavoidable and deeply meaningful responsibilities. She performs all of the functions of a King after having profoundly held the position of Queen. She is an exceptional example of a woman's fortitude and persistence, even though she is naturally regarded as weak. She had to play both a dedicated queen and a loyal wife. She seemed to be fighting against the state's poor and critical conditions. Certainly, she is an ideal emblem of a modern Indian woman who is willing to fight against any injustice, regardless of gender. Tagore created a unique blend of a revolutionary and a traditional Indian woman in Sumitra's persona. She is well-versed in her processes. When she sees Vikram holding his negligence high, she confidently approaches him and says, "Isn't the course clear before you?" "Go with you soldiers and crush these miscreants." (147)

Sumitra portrays Tagore's vision of a powerful woman who is not stifled or subservient, but rather recognised as a complimentary component of man. Tagore's character emphasises the necessity of exhibiting strength and resolve, encouraging humans to have a balanced attitude toward their duties and rights. Sumitra's character combines five aspects of womanhood into one.

- A loving and dedicated beloved
- A caring and active wife
- A thoroughly aware, firmly determined, and daring queen
- A loving and sacrificing sister
- And finally a woman full of self-respect, who courageously accepts death, but does not bow her head before wrong.

Sumitra, without a doubt, represents the modern Indian woman. For her, love empowers the entire personality rather than transforming it into selfishness. A merciful heart cannot see others cry; instead, it strives to make everyone happy.

Ila Embodying Archetypal Virtues and Constrained Femininity

Ila is another really important female character. As we all know, she deserves a lot of credit for playing a crucial role in the play. Ila is a good example of love and beauty. Ila's focused attitude to love claims to have brought about a positive and static shift in Vikram's mindset. Tagore conceived her as a Goddess of Love, and she has been elevated to a higher level of devotion and dedication. In Ila, Tagore admires a woman's stunning beauty while remaining distant from human relationships and needs. She is the personification of beauty, magic, and charm. She is an enduring symbol of love and the desire for beauty in man's heart. The dramatist portrayed Ila in contrast to the play's other female characters. Sumitra, on the other hand, is a primary character, and the entire play is centered on her, yet Ila appears to be

suppressing her in terms of her dedication to her lover Kumarsen. When she refuses King Vikram's love offer “My father has given me to you. I beg myself back from your hands. You have wealth untold, and territories unlimited,—go and leave me behind in the dust; there is nothing that you can want.” He surprisingly asserts, “Is there, indeed, nothing that I can want. How shall I show you my heart? Where is its wealth? Where are its territories? It is empty. Had I no kingdom, but only you—.” She makes an incredible sacrifice

“...first take my life,—as you take that of the wild deer of the forest, piercing her heart with your

arrows,—.” (170) Ila successfully transforms the King's revenge into a pardon, highlighting her beauty as the biggest power on earth along with the most loving and innocent face of womanhood. She expresses her love for her lover, Kumarsen, who has gone to war and left her behind. Ila vows to marry her passionate lover, believing he will return one day. Her complete personality is evident from the beginning of her emergence, and the conversation between the King and Ila showcases her sublime womanly grace. Ila's love for her lover is evident in her determination, “Sire, you are great in power, but what is your power for, if you do not help the great? Can you keep yourself aloof? Then show me the way,—I will offer my life for him,—the one week woman. (172-73)

Ila chooses a tough life with her lover, Kumarsen, despite her innocence and desire for a worldly life. She is portrayed as a tender and effeminate symbol of love, embodying a fond heart full of love. However, her love for her lover is selfish compared to Sumitra's ideological and sacrificing sense. Ila aims to take her lover away from worldly happenings, to a place where no one can interrupt them. The Playwright skillfully differentiates her from other characters, creating a unique and affectionate character. Ila's sacrifices and love for her lover set her apart from the rest of the characters. If we consider the love of King Vikram and Ila, we will notice a significant connection in their experiences with love. Both wish to keep their spouses in their imagined world. Both have a low sense of duty, yet they are not the same. Ila, like Vikram, refuses to blame Kumarsen for anything. Despite stealing her lover's heart, she feels that her silent dedication will win him over. Her love is divine, pure, and honest. Commenting on the basic nature of women Tagore puts forward his views:

A man's interest in his fellow-being becomes real when he finds some special gift of power of usefulness, but a woman feels interest in her fellow-beings because they are living creatures, because they can serve, or some power which they possess and for which she has a special admiration. And because woman has this power, she exercises such charm over minds; her exuberance of vital interest is so attractive that it makes her speech, her laughter, her movement, everything graceful; for the note of gracefulness is in this harmony with all our surrounding interests. (Das, 413)

Revati as a Quintessence of Villainy and Antagonistic Prowess

In contrast to Sumitra and Ila, Tagore depicts a grey aspect of women in Revati, Kumarsen's ruthless and selfish Aunt. Revati believes that money and power are the most important things in the world, and she is willing to kill her nephew, Kumarsen, despite his enormous regard for her. Revati portrays a woman's darkest face. Tagore appears to paint a bleak image of society through Revati's avarice. She wishes to assume control of the realm as Queen. To fulfill her desire for money and power, she directs her husband to profit from the competing

conditions by employing Vikram. When Vikram says, “If he surrenders, I shall pardon him,” she venomously reacts, “Only this, and nothing more? If tame pardon comes at the end, then why is there such preparation? King’s are not overgrown children, and war is not mere child’s play.” (164) She intends to investigate the poisoned state of the woman's mind. She applauds Vikram for taking decisive action against Kumarsen, who is in the forest. To carry out her unscrupulous objectives, she directs the King to burn the villagers' standing crops. This demonstrates the height of a woman's hatred and greed, as she does not hesitate to make a disgusting proposition to the King in order to achieve her vile and selfish goals. This is unquestionably the most horrific act committed by a human being, particularly a woman who embodies the values of compassion and mercy. Revati's avarice and selfishness reveal the King's wicked intentions. This is the first time he realises the foul face of his hatred, and he begins to criticise himself after meeting Revati. Vikram's senses create a new way of looking at life, this time through a woman. He becomes restless and unable to bear the weight of his faults, which are followed by greed and violence. Vikram's confession is sufficient to draw the character of Revati: "Oh, the red flame of hell-fire." Greed and hatred in a woman's heart. I wonder whether I saw my own face in hers. (166)

Women Serve the Catalyst of Change in the Play

Tagore has masterfully synchronised various elements of womanhood in a single thread. Tagore has viewed women as equal participants in all aspects of life. He passionately opposes the notion that women are the replica of men. Tagore has vigorously advocated the notion that women have been endowed with remarkable talents to control society and balance the functions of nature that men lack. Through the figure of Sumitra, Tagore has effectively supported the truth about a woman's true existence, which is not to blindly follow her husband's every request while sitting passively, but to actively participate by realising her rational abilities. All female characters in this drama reflect the three various colours of womanhood. Sumitra is a confident, aware, and bold woman. Ila, an innocent girl who is far away from worldly issues, considers herself Kumarsen's committed sweetheart. Revati has been portrayed as a ruthless, harsh, and nasty woman whose selfishness is excessive. All of them play important roles in painting a complete image of society on the canvas of drama. Sumitra, Ila, and Revati have all succeeded in influencing Vikram's mindset. Each of them presents their perspectives on love, duty, commitment, sacrifice, and selflessness. Tagore believes that if allowed to participate in social activities on an equal footing, a woman can demonstrate surprising talent and mental balance. In the words of the dramatist:

I do not mean to imply that domestic life is the only life for a woman. I mean that the human world is the woman's world, be it domestic or be it full of the other activities of the life, which are humane activities, and not merely abstract efforts to organize. ... She can extend her radiance of love beyond its boundaries on all sides, and even leave it to prove her woman's nature when the call comes to her. (Das, 414)

Tagore teaches through his female characters that a woman must remember that she is not there to replace someone else but to carve out a strong niche for herself. Woman, with her heavenly grace and unchallenging potential, contributes significantly to the development of a fully developed and properly cultured civilization. What is truly required is the recognition of her abilities and caliber. And once she has realised herself, she can construct new myths. Sumitra, for example, works to restore lost social balance by utilising her hidden talents in an area traditionally reserved for men.

Deciphering the Intricate Conventional Symbolism in Tagore's Exploration of Gender Dynamics.

The King and Queen is a fantastic theatrical production. The fundamental theme of the play is conflict and miscommunication. "The conflict in this play is between love and duty, between a vain and infatuated man, and a proud and human woman." (Kriplani, 127) Throughout the play, there is a dominant struggle between King Vikram's lavish display of emotional feelings and Queen Sumitra's exceedingly noble, responsible, and caring personality. The terrible division of the King and Queen has serious ramifications for their relationship. The conflict, which is at the heart of the play, can be seen growing stronger at the start of the play, as the royal couple engages in a contradictory debate. Adopting an unsympathetic attitude towards Sumitra's highly ideological notion of duty and love, he portrays her as guilty, having committed the sin of disobeying her spouse, which he regards as an unpardonable act committed by a woman. The King is unaware of the genuine meaning of a husband-wife connection, and its importance is not considered by him, he always seeks to link his love within his constraints. However, for Sumitra, love has a fleeting meaning. It never binds anyone to the flaws of life; rather, it allows man to fully develop as a human being. Sumitra's magnificence shines through in all of its glory. Sumitra shares Tagore's perspectives on love and duty. Tagore believed "Bondage and liberation are not antagonistic in love. For love is most free and at the same time most bound." (Das, 413) The following comment from Tagore will reveal a glimpse of the play:

The king and the Queen is a composition of my early youth; it was my first attempt to write a play proper. There is a conflict in the relationship of Sumitra and Vikram which is resolved with the death of Sumitra. The overpowering passion thwarting Vikram's complete acceptance of Sumitra is pacified by the death of Sumitra which helps Vikram realizes her true nobility. (Das, 413)

Tagore's play promoted two distinct faces of womanhood: the first takes an enterprising approach to the practical world, undermining the importance of personal life, and the second dedicates herself to every demand of life at the expense of her freedom. Both faces fail to capture the full picture of womanhood that an ideal woman possesses. Sumitra and Ila both claim one stage of femininity. Sumitra is confident, determined, self-aware, forward-thinking, and, most importantly, a comprehensive portrait of a modern Indian woman. Ila, on the other hand, portrays one aspect of femininity. The traits of a complete woman are not well portrayed by Ila either. While Sumitra abandons her marriage to pursue her path, she isolates herself from everything for her lover and asserts that she has no unique personality. Whether portraying Laxmi or Urvashi, Tagore has handled both identities with such skill and has attempted to convey to us the uncommon reality of the world that a woman must give her all in both roles. Despite not being a popular theatrical artist, Tagore contributed to the tradition of modern drama by sustaining the spirit of realism and representing the complexities of women's lives through strong portrayals. His dramatic corpse is a living manifestation of higher human values reflecting Indian women's sensitivity and the tragic conditions they face in society. Tagore's women are gifted with virtues of dynamism and determination, representing a complete picture of Indian womanhood, balancing modern and traditional images of womanhood. These features are well maintained by all his women characters.

Conclusion

Finally, the study brings to the conclusion that Tagore's plays emphasise the spiritual powers of love, dignity, and sublime grace, focusing on women as the main attention. His female characters embody strength and tenderness, showcasing the inner conflicts of women's souls and their mental turmoil. Tagore appears to be more particular while dealing with women. Sumitra, the character in this drama, reflects Tagore's ideal of a cognizant modern Indian woman. As seen by the character of Ila Tagore, she believes that woman is synonymous with love, and that only love can function as a transformative force in life. Sumitra and Ila, the two aspects of femininity, when combined, form a comprehensive picture of womanhood. Tagore has taken a very practical and realistic approach to depicting the practical aspects of women's lives. Here, I'd like to mention Tagore's intimate relationship with Victoria Ocampo, which critics see as one of the most powerful inspirations as well as a source of understanding women's psychology and inner workings. In the words of Ketaki Dyson:

It does seem extremely likely to me that his relationship with Ocampo must have been one of the factors which helped to open him up psychologically towards the feminist issues of the factors which helped to open him up psychologically towards the feminist issues of the times. (Dyson, In Your Blossoming Flower-Garden, 311)

Dyson comments again: “...friendship with a woman like Victoria Ocampo in his mature years may well have deepened his own understanding of the women’s cause.” (313) Tagore's literary career was not a mere passing phase, but an integral part of his creative sensibility. His diverse portrayal of women characters showcases his versatility in presenting modern women who embrace new challenges while maintaining traditional norms and ethics. Examples include Sumitra, Aparna, Nandini, and Srimati. Tagore also delved into women's minds, realistically painting their innermost happenings. Chitra, Prakriti, Ila, and Malati are examples of this trend. He also provided psychological treatment to female characters who were ready to embrace new eras but not completely break away from Indian womanhood. Female figures like Lokesvari, Chandra, Revati, and Gunawati represent this section of Tagore's drama. Tagore was a thinker who used his logic and reasons to deal with his women characters. His women appear to be breaking down age-old traditional constraints of limitation and gradually emerging as a new face of womanhood. Participating in societal functions, they confidently come forward to safeguard their dignity and survival as human beings. And they are not afraid to conduct a war against society to do this. Finally, Tagore’s words will help me summarize the intent of the paper.

I do not mean to imply that domestic life is the only life for a woman. I mean that the human world is the woman’s world, be it domestic or be it full of the other activities of the life, which are humane activities, and not merely abstract efforts to organize. ... She can extend her radiance of love beyond its boundaries on all sides, and even leave it to prove her woman’s nature when the call comes to her. (Das, 414)

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